

LIGHT-ACTUATED REVERSIBLE SHAPE MEMORY EFFECT OF A POLYMER COMPOSITE

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Keywords: Shape memory, light-induced, reversible actuator

ABSTRACT

Traditional shape memory polymers (SMPs) are an exciting class of smart materials that are capable of fixing a temporary shape and recovering to the original shape upon application of appropriate external stimuli [1-13]. This ability has two distinct advantages: first, traditional SMPs can exhibit a series of complex shape transformations (spiral, petal, origami and so on) in response to an external stimulus; second, the original shape can be deformed and reprogrammed multiple times. Due to these unique properties, traditional SMPs have been applied in various fields, such as aerospace field [14], biomedical devices [15], optoelectronic field [16, 17], self-healing materials [18, 19] and information carriers [20, 21]. However, the so-called traditional SMPs with non-reversible one-way shape memory effect (1W-SME) have disadvantages when used in some fields where reversible bidirectional SME are needed.

Most recently, semi-crystalline polymer networks have been reported as an interesting solution towards reversible two-way shape memory effect (2W-SME), because their synthesis is easier and cheaper than liquid crystalline elastomers or other solutions [22-26]. Two strategies have been used to realize this feature. That is, under persistent external mechanical forces [27] or stress free conditions [28], the 2W-SMPs are capable of undergoing reversible dimensional variations between two distinguished geometries when cyclically heated or cooled on specific temperature regions. The actuating mechanism of 2W-SME under constant forces is that the crystalline chain segments crystallize and elongate along the direction of constant forces below the crystallization temperature, and crystal melting induces crystalline chain contraction above the melting temperature [29]. The behavior of 2W-SME under stress free conditions stems from the correlated interplay between a network of chemical cross-links and a crystalline scaffold, each capable of encoding a distinct shape. The relaxation of extended polymer chains on heating is inverted by polymer crystallization along the original pathway on cooling [30]. Currently, the known reversible shape switching of 2W-SMPs is generally observed by outer direct heating and cooling cycles, and the cooling temperatures are low [25, 28]. However, this characteristic of 2W-SMPs restricts their applications in some fields, such as aerospace, and so on. To circumvent this situation, a remotely controlled and reversible 2W-SME with relatively high cooling condition is highly desired.

Accordingly, in this study, a novel polymer composite with an excellent reversible two-way shape memory effect (2W-SME) was fabricated using chemically cross-linked poly (ethylene-co-vinyl acetate) (EVA) as the matrix and *p*-aminodiphenylimide (*p*-AP) as light-absorber and heat source (EVA/*p*-AP). Unlike traditional thermally-driven two-way reversible shape memory polymers, in our concept, the EVA/*p*-AP featured remotely controlled and light-manipulatable reversible two-way shape memory behaviors. Utilizing the distinct light-responsive behavior of *p*-AP in the irradiation of 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) light, the EVA/*p*-AP composite exhibited excellent light-actuated reversible 2W-SME by a light-manipulated procedure. The results from this study showed that the material could have good potential applications in soft reversible drivers.

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